

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BRUCE****FIRST NAME: JULIAN****PROGRAM CODE: DRTM****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: QUIZ****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied the US grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 02%

The author used the following software: Windows 11, Google Docs

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following should be included as a dissertation chapter?
 - Ethical Considerations
 - Limitations and Delimitations
 - Issues of Trustworthiness
 - Methodology and Research Approach¹**

2. Which of the following describes the “theoretical conceptual framework” of a dissertation?
 - Related to the problem statement, purpose, and research questions

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 73.

- Draws on theory, research and experience and examines the relationships among constructs and ideas²**
 - Integrates key themes and issues emanating from the review
 - Describes the content, scope, and organization of the review as well as all the strategies used in the literature search
3. Which of the following is a frequent error within the “findings” section?
- Data are not clearly presented
 - Study findings are manipulated to fit expectations from research questions³**
 - The introduction does not clearly reflect the study’s components and/or the relationship of methodological choices to the proposed research problem and purpose
 - The overgeneralization of importance or relevance leads to grandiose statements
4. Which of the following are quality markers of the “literature review” section of a dissertation?
- A clear description of the research sample, setting, methodology, limitations and delimitations, and acknowledgement of trustworthiness
 - Clear, complete, and credible representation of data that have emerged as a result of the study and effective use of graphs, charts and other visual representations to illustrate the data

² Ibid., 77-78.

³ Ibid., 84.

- A comprehensive and thoughtful selection of resources directly related to the study's purpose and background⁴**
 - An integration of the study findings, analysis, interpretation, and synthesis
5. Which of the following is a reason for the “conclusions and recommendations” section of a dissertation?
- To discover what meaning you as the researcher can make by comparing your findings both within and across groups, and with those of other studies
 - Making sense of large amounts of material, reducing raw data, identifying what is significant, and constructing a framework for communicating the essence of what the data reveal
 - Reflects the contribution the researcher has made to the knowledge, practice, and/or policy in the field of study⁵**
 - Provides a strong theoretical or conceptual basis for the dissertation by analyzing and synthesizing a comprehensive selection of appropriately related bodies of literature
6. Which of the following is the appropriate use of a semicolon (;)?
- To separate main clauses that have different subjects and are not connected by a conjunction⁶**
 - To introduce a list or series

⁴ Ibid., 78.

⁵ Ibid., 87-88.

⁶ World Health Organization. *WHO Editorial Style Manual* (Geneva: World Health Organization Press, 1993), 32.

- To indicate that a second statement explains or amplifies the first
 - To indicate parenthetical expression
7. What is the appropriate way to cite unpublished information?
- ([name of institution], [name of the authority cited], unpublished data or unpublished observations or personal communication, [date])
 - (**[name of the authority cited], [name of institution], unpublished data or unpublished observations or personal communication, [date]**)⁷
 - (unpublished data or unpublished observations or personal communication, [name of institution], [name of the authority cited], [date])
 - ([date], [name of the authority cited], [name of institution], unpublished data or unpublished observations or personal communication)
8. What is the proper usage of the en rule (—)?
- To denote time periods, such as academic and fiscal years, that encompass parts of two consecutive calendar years, and to link two words that can be used interchangeably
 - To show joint possession
 - To mark an omission in a quotation
 - To indicate a close relationship between two nouns**⁸
9. When is it acceptable to omit a citation?

⁷ Ibid., 36.

⁸ Ibid., 34-35.

- When the information is part of a field's common knowledge⁹**
- When the information is associated with a specific person
- When the information is taken from a web source that is free and widely available
- When the information is paraphrased

10. Which type of graph compares three variables at multiple points of a single case?

- Area chart
- Pie chart
- Histogram
- Bubble chart¹⁰**

⁹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph Bizup, Williams Fitzgerald, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Ninth ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018) 82.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 103-105.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph Bizup, Williams Fitzgerald, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 9th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

World Health Organization. *WHO Editorial Style Manual*. Geneva: World Health Organization Press, 1993.

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